

Analysis of Figurative Language in Album *The Car* by Arctic Monkeys

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ABSTRACT: This research explores the use of figurative language in the album *The Car* by Arctic Monkeys, focusing on its role in enhancing lyrical depth within the alternative rock genre. The main objectives are to identify the types of figurative language used and determine the most prevalent type in the album's lyrics. A descriptive qualitative research design was employed, with data collected by active listening and recording of linguistic phenomena, specifically by analyzing lyrics from the Genius website and listening to the album on Spotify. The analysis was guided by Perrine's (2017) framework, which categorizes figurative language into 12 types: simile, metaphor, personification, apostrophe, synecdoche, metonymy, symbol, allegory, paradox, hyperbole, understatement, and irony. The findings reveal 64 instances of figurative language across the album's 10 songs, with metaphor being the most frequent (22 instances), followed by symbol (14 instances), irony (11 instances), personification (7 instances), hyperbole (4 instances), paradox (3 instances), understatement (1 instance), simile (1 instance), and synecdoche (1 instance). Notably, apostrophe, metonymy, and allegory were absent. The study concludes that figurative language significantly enriches the artistic expression of *The Car*, making the lyrics more engaging and emotionally resonant. These findings contribute to understanding the creative use of language in alternative rock music.

Keywords: figurative language, Arctic Monkeys, song lyrics, *The Car*, music analysis

Language is a system of communication that allows humans to express thoughts, emotions, and ideas through spoken, written, or symbolic forms (Noermanzah, 2019). In addition to its basic function as a means of communication, language also serves as an artistic tool, especially in literature and music. One of the most important elements that can improve the use of language in creative expression is figurative language. Figurative language or known as figures of speech, is a style of language used by the author/speaker to convey a message imaginatively and metaphorically with the aim of creating a certain effect on the reader/listener through the style of language used (Zukhruf & Mas'ad, 2024).

In the term of music, figurative language plays an important part in shaping the poetic and aesthetic quality of song lyrics. Artists and songwriters use literary devices such as metaphors, similes, personification, and hyperbole to convey complex emotions and narratives in a way that resonates with listeners. Several similar previous studies have explained the use of figurative

language in songs. Research by Sihotang et al. (2024) that explained four types of figurative language which appear frequently in the lyrics of Bruno Mars album: personification, metaphor, simile, and eponym. The incorporation of figurative language in the musical compositions of Bruno Mars serves a dual purpose. Firstly, it renders the message conveyed more appealing to listeners. Secondly, it facilitates the comprehension of the song's lyrics by listeners. In addition, the study conducted by Zolkifli & Gani (2024) with the title *The Use of Figurative Language in Feminist Songs*. The objective of this research is to identify figurative language in Taylor Swift's feminist songs. Descriptive qualitative is the method used in this research. The present study employs a data-analytical approach grounded in Alan Bryman's (2012). The findings indicate that feminist ideas find efficacious expression through musical mediums, while figurative language serves as a particularly effective means of articulating feminism within musical compositions. Moreover, previous study is by Tambunsaribu & Sigalingging (2024) which entitled *The Use of Figurative Language and Imagery in Songs' Lyrics*. This study is concerned with the analysis of figurative language and imagery as manifested in the lyrics of two songs from Bruno Mars' album entitled "Talking to the Moon" and "It Will Rain". The present study employs a descriptive qualitative approach. The research revealed that the figurative language and imagery employed in Bruno Mars' songs serve as a means of indirect expression of the author's sentiments. The analysis identified "hyperbole" as the most prevalent figurative device in the lyrics.

The gap between previous studies and this research lies in subject focus and genre. As previous studies have examined figurative language in the lyrics of Bruno Mars and Taylor Swift, no research has specifically analyzed the Arctic Monkeys' album *The Car*. This study offers new insights into an album that has not been studied much, especially in the alternative rock genre. Pop and R&B have been studied before, but this research focuses on the poetic, abstract, and narrative-driven style of Arctic Monkeys' songwriting. This difference in genre may influence the

types and frequency of figurative language used in the lyrics. This study fills a gap by not only analyzing the figurative language used in album *The Car*, but also considering how the band's stylistic choices in an alternative rock context set it apart from the pop-oriented studies that have been conducted previously. Specifically, this research has two objectives: (1) To find the types of figurative language used in the album *The Car* by Arctic Monkeys and (2) To find the type of figurative language that is most commonly used in the album *The Car* by Arctic Monkeys.

This study deepens the understanding of how language functions creatively in music and supports previous research while exploring a new genre and artist. The findings also offer practical value for educators, songwriters, and listeners by demonstrating how figurative language can enrich both lyric analysis and musical appreciation.

METHOD

This research aimed to identify the figurative language contained in the song lyrics in album *The Car* by Arctic Monkeys and decided which kind of figurative language that is commonly used in that album. As stated by Taylor et al. (2016), qualitative research can be defined as a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words or in the form of observed behavior from individuals. The data collection method employed in this study entailed the active listening and recording of linguistic phenomena by accessing the Spotify application to listen to all songs by the band Arctic Monkeys from their album, *The Car*, opening the Genius website (<https://genius.com/albums/Arctic-monkeys/The-car>) to see the song lyrics, and identifying the various types of figurative language present in the lyrics and determining the most frequently used types. To achieve data validity, lyrics were collected from multiple sources. Genius website served as the primary source. Additionally, the songs were actively listened to on the Spotify application to confirm the accuracy of the lyrics. Furthermore, the identification of figurative language was guided by Perrine's (2017) established framework. This

ensured that the classification of figurative language was conducted systematically by using a clear theoretical framework. To ensure reliability, a consistent and repeatable data collection and analysis process was followed. The data collection technique involved all ten tracks of the album *The Car* being actively listened to and the lyrics obtained from the Genius website being analyzed. This process was systematically conducted for each song to ensure uniformity in identifying figurative language. Each instance of figurative language was documented in detailed tables, specifying the lyric, the type of figurative language, and its interpretation. Additionally, the analysis was conducted multiple times to ensure consistency in identification and categorization, thereby reducing the risk of oversight or misinterpretation. Any discrepancies in classification were revisited and resolved through re-examination of the lyrics in the context of Perrine’s (2017) theory.

FINDINGS

This research focused on several types of figurative language in the album *The Car* by Arctic Monkeys. This section contains the collected data, presented in table form to facilitate identification of the number of types of figurative language found in the lyrics of songs on *The Car* album. The table 4.1 below shows the results of an analysis of the figurative language found in the song “There'd Better Be a Mirrorball”.

Table 1. There’d Better Be a Mirrorball

No	Lyrics	Types of Figurative Language
1.	“Yesterday's still leaking through the roof”	Metaphor
2.	“I'll have a heavy heart”	Metaphor
3.	“That there's a mirrorball?”	Symbol

4.	“I'd throw the rose tint back on the exploded view”	Metaphor
5	“And how's that insatiable appetite?”	Irony

Table 1 shows the figurative language used in the song “There'd Better Be a Mirrorball.” There are four types of figurative language: one personification, three metaphors, one symbol, and one irony. Of these four types of figurative language, metaphor is the most frequently used in this song.

Table 2. I Ain't Quite Where I Think I Am

No	Lyrics	Types of Figurative Language
1.	“Freaky keypad by the retina scan”	Metaphor
2.	“I ain't quite where I think I am”	Paradox
3.	“The disco strobes in the stumbling blocks”	Symbol
4.	“Formation displays of affection fly over roll (Eyes back)”	Irony
5	“Blank expressions invite me to suspect”	Personification
6.	“Stackable party guests”	Metaphor
7.	“The spare set of tingles'll race up your spine”	Metaphor
8.	“Looks like the Riviera is coming into land”	Symbol
9.	“And I can see both islands now”	Symbol

From Table 2, it can be seen that in the song entitled “I Ain't Quite Where I Think I Am”, there are five types of figurative language, consisting of three metaphors, one paradox, three symbols, one irony, and one personification. The types of figurative language most frequently

used in this song are metaphors and symbols.

Table 3. Sculptures of Anything Goes

No.	Lyrics	Types of Figurative Language
1.	“How am I supposed to manage my infallible beliefs”	Irony
2.	“Performin' in Spanish on Italian TV”	Irony
3.	“Blank canvasses leant against gallery walls”	Symbol
4.	“Flowing towards sculptures of Anything Goes”	Metaphor
5.	“Is that vague sense of longing kinda trying to cause a scene?”	Personification
6.	“Puncturing your bubble of relatability”	Metaphor
7.	“Baby, those mixed messages ain't what they used to be”	Irony
8.	“The simulation cartridge for City Life ‘09”	Metaphor
9.	“Flash that angle grinder smile”	Metaphor
10.	“From the chandelier and twizzling 'round an umbrella”	Symbol

Based on the analysis that presents in the table 3, the song entitled “Sculptures of Anything Goes” contains five types of figurative language: three irony, two symbol, four metaphor, and one personification. The most prevalent figurative language employed in this song is **metaphor**.

Table 4. Jet Skies on the Moat

No.	Lyrics	Types of Figurative Language
1.	“Jet skis on the moat”	Metaphor, Symbol
2.	“They shot it all in CinemaScope”	Irony
3.	“Showstoppers anonymous”	Personification
4.	“sit there and watch while the paint job dries”	Symbol

5. "Lights out on the Wonder Park"	Metaphor
6. "Your saw-toothed lover boy was quick off the mark"	Metaphor
7. "That's long enough in the sunshine for one night"	Irony
8. "You know that it's alright if you wanna cry"	Understatement

According to the analysis shown in Table 4, the song entitled "Jet Skies on the Moat" features four different types of figurative language: three metaphors, three symbol, one personification, one irony, and one understatement. The most frequently used figurative language in this song is metaphor and symbol.

Table 5. Body Paint

No.	Lyrics	Types of Figurative Language
1.	"So you don't let the sun catch you crying"	Personification
2.	"So predictable, I know what you're thinking"	Irony
3.	"My teeth are beating and my knees are weak"	Metaphor
4.	"I'm watching your every move"	Hyperbole
5.	"Straight from the cover shoot"	Symbol
6.	"And if you're thinking of me I'm probably thinking of you"	Paradox
7.	"There's still a trace of body paint On your legs and on your arms and on your face"	Metaphor

The analysis presented in Table 5 reveals that the song "Body Paint" incorporates six distinct types of figurative language: one personification, one irony, two metaphor, one hyperbole, one symbol, and one paradox. Among these, metaphor and symbol are the most commonly used forms of figurative language in the song.

Table 6. The Car

No.	Lyrics	Types of Figurative Language
1.	“Tryin' to adjust to what's been there all along”	Paradox
2.	“But it ain't a holiday until/You go to fetch somethin' from the car”	Symbol
3.	“And you pretend to fall asleep on the way back”	Metaphor

The findings shown in Table 6 indicate that the song "The Car" features three different types of figurative language: one paradox, one symbol, and one metaphor. The analysis indicates that each figurative language type is represented on a single occasion. Consequently, no particular figurative language type is predominant in "The Car."

Table 7. Big Ideas

No.	Lyrics	Types of Figurative Language
1.	“The ballad of what could've been”	Metaphor
2.	“Over and out It's been a thrill”	Irony
3.	“the orchestra's got us all surrounded”	Metaphor
4.	“And I cannot for the life of me remember how they go”	Hyperbole

Based on the analysis in Table 7, the song “Big Ideas” incorporates four distinct forms of figurative language: two metaphor, one irony, and one hyperbole, with metaphor being the most prevalent.

Table 8. Hello You

No.	Lyrics	Types of Figurative Language
1.	“Lego Napoleon movie, Written in noble gas-filled glass tubes”	Metaphor
2.	“Underlined in sparks”	Symbol
3.	“The Business they call Show, Hasn't ever been this pumped up before”	Personification
4.	“Hello you, still draggin' out a long goodbye?”	Irony
5.	“This electric warrior's motorcade, Shall burn no more rubber down that boulevard”	Symbol
6.	“Takin' a dive into your crystal ball”	Metaphor
7.	“I could pass for seventeen if I just get a shave and catch some Z's”	Hyperbole

As illustrated in Table 8, the song "Hello You" employs figurative language. The following five types of figurative language are identified: two metaphors, two symbol, one personification, one irony, and one hyperbole.

Table 9. Mr Schwartz

No.	Lyrics	Types of Figurative Language
1.	“Put your heavy metal to the test”	Metaphor
2.	“Wardrobe's lint-rollin' your velveteen suit and smudgin' dubbin' on your dancin' shoes”	Symbol
3.	“It's like your little directorial debut”	Simile
4.	“As fine a time as any to deduce, The fact that neither you or I has ever had a clue”	Irony
5.	“The gloved hand's reachin' in to hit the switch”	Personification
6.	“Mr. Schwartz is havin' tea with the grips”	Synecdoche

As demonstrated in Table 9, an analysis of the song "Mr. Schwartz" reveals the presence

of six distinct forms of figurative language: one metaphor, one symbol, one simile, one irony, one personification, and one synecdoche. Based on the analysis, each type of figurative language appears once, so there is no single dominant type in “Mr. Schwartz.”

Table 10. Perfect sense

No.	Lyrics	Types of Figurative Language
1.	“A four-figure sum on a hotel notepad”	Hyperbole
2.	“A revelation or your money back”	Irony
3.	“When my invincible streak turns onto the final straight”	Metaphor

As indicated in Table 10, the song "Perfect Sense" employs figurative language. The following three types of figurative language are identified: one hyperbole, one irony, and one metaphor. According to the analysis, each figure of speech is represented only once. As a result, no particular figure of speech stands out as predominant in "Perfect Sense."

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

After reading and analysing the lyrics on the album “The Car” by Arctic Monkeys, there were various types of figurative language in each song. Table 11 presents the frequency of figurative language in the song lyrics on the album “The Car”.

Table 1. Frequency of Figurative Language

No.	Types of Figurative Language	Frequency
1.	Metaphor	22
2.	Symbol	14
3.	Irony	11
4.	Personification	7
5.	Hyperbole	4

6.	Paradox	3
7.	Understatement	1
8.	Simile	1
9.	Synecdoche	1
10.	Apostrophe	0
11.	Metonymy	0
12.	Allegory	0
Total		64

In the album “The Car” by Arctic Monkeys, there are 64 phrases and sentences in the song lyrics that utilize figurative language. As demonstrated in table 11, the most commonly used figurative language in the songs contained the album "The Car" is metaphor, followed by symbol, irony, personification, hyperbole, paradox, understatement, simile, and synecdoche in descending order of frequency. Conversely, the songs exhibit an absence of figurative language, including apostrophe, metonymy, and allegory. Below is an explanation of each lyric in the album “The Car” based on each type of figurative language.

1. Metaphor

The figurative language that commonly used in this album is metaphor. There are 22 phrases and sentences that the writer found. According to Anggraeni and Dewi (2023), metaphor is a figure of speech that compares two things that are not related by stating that one is the other. Here are 22 examples of metaphors identified in the lyrics of Arctic Monkeys’ album "The Car" with the explanation in each lyric.

1. *“Somehow giving it the old romantic fool”*

The singer compares himself indirectly to a “romantic fool,” portraying himself as someone hopelessly sentimental.

2. *“I’ll have a heavy heart”*

“Heavy heart” does not literally mean increased weight but signifies deep sorrow or emotional burden.

3. *“I'd throw the rose tint back on the exploded view”*

“Rose tint” refers to looking at things in a positive way. An “exploded view” means something broken or chaotic. This lyric shows the singer trying to see a broken relationship in a positive way.

4. *“Freaky keypad by the retina scan”*

This phrase creates an image that is strange and like something from the future. It describes a place that feels high-tech, which reflects the singer’s feeling of being out of place and trapped.

5. *“Stackable party guests”*

People are not objects that can be stacked. This metaphor suggests that the guests are being treated like decorations or props, not real people. It makes the setting seem fake and meaningless.

6. *“The spare set of tingles'll race up your spine”*

“Tingles racing up your spine” is a way of describing a sudden emotional reaction. It may describe excitement or fear.

7. *“Flowing towards sculptures of Anything Goes”*

The phrase “sculptures of anything goes” is not literal. There is no real sculpture that represents “anything goes.” They represent freedom without meaning. Things that look beautiful but have no rules or structure.

8. *“Puncturing your bubble of relatability”*

There is no real “bubble” around someone. The bubble represents someone’s comfort or identity. Saying it’s “punctured” means breaking that connection.

9. *“The simulation cartridge for City Life ‘09”*

Life is compared to a video game or simulation. A "cartridge" is something you plug in to play a game. This implies that life feels artificial, not real. The singer might feel like he is just playing a role in a fake world.

10. *"Flash that angle grinder smile"*

A person's smile is being compared to an angle grinder (a loud, rough tool). This means the smile is probably fake, forced, or uncomfortable.

11. *"Jet skis on the moat"*

A moat is the water around a castle for protection, and jet skis are fast, fun vehicles. Putting jet skis on a moat is unusual. It mixes something playful with something serious.

12. *"Lights out on the Wonder Park"*

The word "Wonder Park" probably is not a real place; instead, it serves as a metaphor for a time or place filled with joy that has now passed. The phrase "lights out" signifies the end of something special.

13. *"Your saw-toothed lover boy was quick off the mark"*

"Saw-toothed" describes someone's personality as sharp and jagged, not smooth and gentle. This makes the person look aggressive, dangerous, and even cruel in love.

14. *"My teeth are beating and my knees are weak"*

Teeth cannot actually "beat," but this expression illustrates a physical response to intense emotions such as anxiety or anger. Similarly, the phrase "knees are weak" implies emotional or physical instability rather than a lack of physical strength.

15. *"There's still a trace of body paint/On your legs and on your arms and on your face"*

"Body paint" probably represents memories, lies, or scars from the past. This shows that something (or someone) is still visible, even if it is meant to be hidden.

16. *"And you pretend to fall asleep on the way back"*

This line suggests avoiding reality or the pressures of the moment. The phrase "falling asleep" does not literally mean sleeping. It is a way of emotionally withdrawing or faking indifference to escape others' demands.

17. *"The ballad of what could've been"*

There is no real ballad being sung. The speaker is using "ballad" as a metaphor for a memory or emotional story about missed opportunities.

18. *"the orchestra's got us all surrounded"*

This line does not literally mean an orchestra is physically surrounding the speaker. Instead, it compares the overwhelming pressure or chaos of a situation to being encircled by an orchestra.

19. *"Lego Napoleon movie/Written in noble gas-filled glass tubes"*

This phrase does not refer to an actual film. The "Lego Napoleon movie" implies something that is built and artificial, while "noble gas-filled glass tubes" conjures a surreal, technological vibe.

20. *"Takin' a dive into your crystal ball"*

This line represents the singer's attempt to understand or predict someone's thoughts or future.

21. *"Put your heavy metal to the test"*

The term "heavy metal" does not literally refer to the music genre or metallic material, but rather, it is used metaphorically to suggest something intense, bold, or emotionally weighty, such as the singer's feelings or a challenge. The phrase "put to the test" implies evaluating this intensity by comparing it to a trial or experiment.

22. *"When my invincible streak turns onto the final straight"*

The phrase "invincible streak" compares the singer's period of success or confidence to an

unbroken winning streak. The term “streak” represents the singer’s personal sense of being unstoppable.

The 22 phrases and sentences identified in the Arctic Monkeys' album “The Car” can be considered metaphors because they use figurative language to draw comparisons between seemingly unrelated concepts, thereby enriching the meaning and emotional depth of the lyrics. This is in line with Anggraeni and Dewi (2023) explanation of metaphor that said a metaphor is a type of figurative language that makes a comparison between two things that are not usually compared. One example of metaphor in the song lyrics in album “The Car” is *“Somehow giving it the old romantic fool”*. It compares the singer to a "romantic fool." This implies that the singer is aware that their feelings are too intense. The metaphor suggests that the singer's actions might seem irrational or overly idealistic, driven by romantic impulses that don't align with reality. Similarly with the lyric *“I’ll have a heavy heart.”* The term "heavy heart" does not literally refer to increased weight but instead conveys profound sorrow or an overwhelming emotional burden. Each metaphor illustrates complex feelings by equating one idea with another, enabling listeners to engage with the themes on a deeper level.

2. Symbol

The second figurative language that commonly used in this album is symbol. Perrine (2017) stated that symbol is the phenomenon in which a word possesses its own meaning while representing something entirely different. The following is a list of 14 examples of symbol identified in the lyrics of the album “The Car” by Arctic Monkeys.

1. *“That there’s a mirrorball”*

A mirrorball (disco ball) literally refers to a sparkling ball used in dance halls. But this lyric symbolizes something more, perhaps romance, beauty, hope, or closure. The singer wants to end this emotional moment with something magical, not just sadness.

2. *“The disco strobes in the stumbling blocks”*

Disco lights are a symbol of glamour and excitement, and "stumbling blocks" represent obstacles or difficulties. They show that life can look fun on the outside, but is actually full of struggles.

3. *“Looks like the Riviera is coming into land”*

"The Riviera" symbolizes beauty and luxury. Saying it's "coming into land" could mean something glamorous is arriving, maybe a fantasy or an illusion.

4. *“And I can see both islands now”*

Seeing "both islands" can symbolize a broader perspective or understanding. It is as if the singer recognizes the different aspects of a situation or relationship.

5. *“Blank canvasses leant against gallery walls”*

A blank canvas normally represents something unfinished. In this lyric, it symbolizes emptiness or emotional confusion. It stands for unexpressed feelings or an unclear relationship.

6. *“From the chandelier and twizzling 'round an umbrella”*

Spinning around with an umbrella symbolize chaos, confusion, or childlike escape.

7. *“Jet skis on the moat”*

This symbolizes wasting fun or luxury in the wrong place, or using fun to cover up emotional protection or defense. It feels out of place.

8. *“They shot it all in CinemaScope”*

CinemaScope is a wide film format used in movies, especially dramatic or romantic scenes. Saying something was “shot in CinemaScope” suggests life is being lived like a movie. It symbolizes in how people live or remember experiences.

9. *“sit there and watch while the paint job dries”*

Watching paint dry is known to be boring. This line suggests the person is just sitting there

doing nothing or ignoring something important.

10. *“Straight from the cover shoot”*

A “cover shoot” means a photo for a magazine, often polished and perfect. This symbolizes beauty, image, or performance. The person looks flawless, but maybe it is all for show.

11. *“But it ain't a holiday until/You go to fetch somethin' from the car”*

This recurring line symbolizes family routines and moments that define trips and shared memories. It is not about actually getting something from the car, but it is about the little, familiar details that make something feel warm and inviting.

12. *“Underlined in sparks”*

"Sparks" do not literally underline anything. Instead, they suggest excitement, intensity, or danger. Saying that something is "underlined in sparks" implies that what's being said is emotionally or dramatically important.

13. *“This electric warrior's motorcade/Shall burn no more rubber down that boulevard”*

The “electric warrior” likely represents a passionate or rebellious part of someone’s identity, and the “motorcade” is the vehicle of that identity. Saying it “shall burn no more rubber” symbolizes the end of bold movement or rebellion.

14. *“Wardrobe's lint-rollin' your velveteen suit and smudgin' dubbin' on your dancin' shoes”*

The “velveteen suit” and “dancin’ shoes” symbolize preparation, performance, or a polished persona, possibly for a role in a show or life itself. “Dubbin” (a wax for polishing shoes) adds to the idea of perfecting this outward appearance.

The 14 phrases and sentences in the Arctic Monkeys' album "The Car" can be considered as symbols. This is because they use words that have their own literal meaning. These symbols represent deeper, often abstract concepts. This makes the lyrics more emotional and thematic. This concept aligns with Perrine’s (2017) definition of a symbol, that a symbol has its own

meaning while also representing something else. One example of a symbol in the album's lyrics is *"That there's a mirrorball."* The mirrorball is a sparkling dance hall object that symbolizes romance, beauty, hope, or a sense of closure. It evokes a magical moment amidst emotional complexity. Similarly, *"The disco strobes in the stumbling blocks"* uses disco lights to symbolize fun and excitement, while "stumbling blocks" represent life's obstacles, showing the contrast between a dazzling exterior and internal struggles. Another example is the phrase *"Looks like the Riviera is coming into land."* Here, "the Riviera" represents beauty and luxury. It suggests the arrival of a glamorous yet possibly unrealistic fantasy.

3. Irony

The third figurative language that commonly used in the song lyrics in album "The Car" is irony. As stated by Kayla and Simatupang (2025), irony is a contrast between expectation and reality. Below is a compilation of 11 instances of irony found in the lyrics of Arctic Monkeys' album "The Car."

1. *"How's that insatiable appetite"*

This sounds sarcastic. He is not really asking about someone's hunger. Instead, he might be mocking their endless desire for attention, drama, or emotional satisfaction.

2. *"Formation displays of affection fly over (Eyes roll back)"*

The lyrics talk about a big display of affection in public, but people's reactions are more like rolling their eyes. This shows that they are not interested or bothered. This is verbal irony, where the singer finds the romantic gesture not believable or excessive.

3. *"How am I supposed to manage my infallible beliefs"*

The word "infallible" means "perfect" or "never wrong." However, in this line the singer seems to doubt himself, asking how he can manage those beliefs. It is ironic because he claims his beliefs are perfect, but also suggests he is overwhelmed or confused by them.

4. *“Performin' in Spanish on Italian TV”*

This lyric describes an odd situation, which is performing in a language not native to the country. It is meant to highlight how strange or disconnected things feel. The scene is so mismatched, it becomes ironic.

5. *“Baby, those mixed messages ain't what they used to be”*

Saying “mixed messages” used to be better is sarcastic. It is illogical because confusion should not be admired. The singer is mocking emotional inconsistency.

6. *“That's long enough in the sunshine for one night”*

It is contradictory to have sunshine at night. Claiming to have had enough sunshine at night mocks or reflects the exhaustion that comes with pretending things are okay.

7. *“So predictable, I know what you're thinking”*

The singer claims to know what the other person is thinking, implying their actions are unoriginal and expected. The line sounds casual, but it actually reflects disappointment or sarcasm.

8. *“Over and out/It's been a thrill”*

Although the phrase sounds like a cheerful goodbye, it is likely used with a tone of disappointment or emotional exhaustion. Though it may seem light, in context it is bitter or sarcastic.

9. *“Hello you, still draggin' out a long goodbye?”*

The singer is likely mocking or highlighting the other person’s reluctance to fully end a relationship or situation, implying it is unnecessarily prolonged.

10. *“As fine a time as any to deduce / That neither you nor I has ever had a clue”*

This lyric is irony because it casually implies that both individuals are unaware, even though they have been going through life without true comprehension.

11. *"A revelation or your money back"*

The singer may be mocking the notion that profound emotional experiences can be simplified into a transactional exchange. This illustrates the absurdity of expecting guaranteed results in life or relationships.

The 11 phrases and sentences in the Arctic Monkeys' album "The Car" considered as irony. They make a contrast between what we expect and what actually happens. The lyrics have different layers of sarcasm, mockery, and unexpected twists. This lines up with Kayla and Simatupang's (2025) take on irony as the difference between what is expected and what actually happens. One example of irony in the album's lyrics is *"How's that insatiable appetite."* It seems like this line is supposed to be about someone's hunger, but it is probably a sarcastic comment about their constant need for attention or drama. It is more of a joke than a real question. irony shows a difference between how something looks and what it really is, and it makes listeners think about the deeper emotional or critical sides of the lyrics.

4. Personification

Personification is the fourth figurative language that commonly used in album "The Car". Personification is a phrase that uses objects, animals, or abstract concepts to create that the object can be alive like a human (Saputris, 2025). The following section provides a collection of seven examples of personification found in the lyrics of Arctic Monkeys' album "The Car."

1. *"Yesterday's still leaking through the roof"*

"Yesterday" (a time or memory) is described as if it can leak like water. Time does not actually leak, so this is personification. It suggests that the past is still affecting the present. In other words, he can't move on.

2. *"Blank expressions invite me to suspect"*

"Blank expressions" are given a human action. they "invite" suspicion. This makes it sound

like the expressions are actively encouraging the singer to feel suspicious.

3. *“Is that vague sense of longing kinda trying to cause a scene?”*

A feeling (longing) is described as if it has the power to create a dramatic scene, much like a person would.

4. *“Showstoppers anonymous”*

A “showstopper” refers to something remarkable in a performance, while “anonymous” means hidden or unknown. In this context, showstoppers are treated like people in a group.

5. *“So you don’t let the sun catch you crying”*

The sun is described as if it can “catch you crying,” like a person walking in on you during a vulnerable moment.

6. *“The Business they call Show/Hasn't ever been this pumped up before”*

“The Business they call Show,” presumably referring to show business or the entertainment industry, is attributed with the human trait of being “pumped up,” meaning excited or energized.

7. *“The gloved hand's reachin' in to hit the switch”*

“The gloved hand” is given the human actions of “reaching” and “hitting the snooze,” as if it has intent or agency. While it could refer to a person, the focus on the “gloved hand” as a standalone entity personifies it, emphasizing the action over the actor.

The seven phrases and sentences in the Arctic Monkeys' album “The Car” considered personification because they give human-like qualities or actions to things like abstract ideas or non-human entities. This matches up with Saputris's (2025) idea of personification as a way of making things like objects, animals, or abstract ideas seem like they have human qualities. One example of personification in the album's lyrics is *“Yesterday's still leaking through the roof.”* The idea of “yesterday,” as in a time or memory, is described as if it can seep in like water, making

it seem like the past continues to impact the present. This evokes a feeling of emotional weight that lingers.

5. Hyperbole

The other figurative language that commonly used is hyperbole. Hyperbole is a rhetorical device in which an expression is used in excess to emphasize a point or a situation (Perrine, 2017).

The following section offers a collection of four s

1. *"I'm watching your every move"*

The singer is not literally watching every move. This is an exaggerated way of expressing obsession, suspicion, or intense focus.

2. *"And I cannot for the life of me remember how they go"*

The phrase "for the life of me" is an exaggeration. No one's life depends on remembering melodies. It dramatically exaggerates a sense of profound frustration or inability.

3. *"I could pass for seventeen if I just get a shave and catch some Z's"*

The claim that the singer could "pass for seventeen" with just a shave and some sleep is an exaggeration. It emphasizes a desire to feel youthful or start anew, but it is unlikely a simple shave and rest could make someone appear so much younger.

4. *"A four-figure sum on a hotel notepad"*

the phrase "a four-figure sum on a hotel notepad" is a hyperbole, exaggerating the cost of writing something on a notepad. A "four-figure sum" is an absurdly high value for a simple note written on hotel stationery.

The four phrases and sentences identified in the Arctic Monkeys' album "The Car" can be considered hyperbole because they use exaggerated expressions to emphasize emotions, situations, or ideas, amplifying their impact within the lyrics. This aligns with Perrine's (2017) definition of hyperbole as a rhetorical device that employs excessive expression to highlight a

point or situation. One example of hyperbole in the album's lyrics is *"I'm watching your every move."* This phrase does not literally mean the singer is observing every action but exaggerates to convey intense focus, obsession, or suspicion.

6. Paradox

Another figurative language used in this album is paradox. as explained by Anggreani and Dewi (2023), paradox is the statement seemingly self-contradiction or opposed to what is commonly held to be true but which nevertheless contains a truth. This section presents a set of three examples illustrating the use of paradox in the lyrics of Arctic Monkeys' album "The Car."

1. *"I ain't quite where I think I am"*

This is a paradox because the singer says he is not where he thinks he is, which sounds confusing. It means he feels mentally or emotionally disconnected from his surroundings. He might be physically somewhere, but emotionally he feels elsewhere or unsure of what is real.

2. *"And if you're thinking of me/I'm probably thinking of you"*

It sounds romantic, but it is also uncertain. The singer does not know for sure. It shows emotional uncertainty, wanting to feel connected but not knowing if the other person feels the same.

3. *"Tryin' to adjust to what's been there all along"*

This line sounds contradictory. How can someone "adjust" to something that is already there? This means that everyone sometimes struggles to accept or internalize things they have always known.

The three phrases and sentences in the Arctic Monkeys' album "The Car" considered as paradox. They seem to say things that do not make sense on the surface, or that go against what most people expect, but they actually reveal deeper truths about how people feel or think. This in line with what Anggreani and Dewi (2023) said about how a paradox is basically a statement that

seems self-contradictory or goes against what most people think, but actually has an underlying truth. One example of a paradox in the album's lyrics is "*I ain't quite where I think I am.*" This statement is paradox because it suggests the singer's perception of his location or state of mind conflicts with reality, reflecting a sense of emotional or mental disconnection.

7. Understatement

The next figurative language is understatement. According to Perrine (2017), understatement is an idiom that employs a conservative expression with double negation. The example, "*You know that it's alright if you wanna cry,*" understates the act of crying by casually describing it as "alright," despite crying typically signifying deep emotional distress.

The phrase identified considered an understatement because it employs a restrained expression to downplay the significance of an emotional act, thereby creating a subtle yet profound effect in the lyrics. This aligns with Perrine's (2017) definition of understatement as an idiom that uses a conservative expression, often with double negation, to minimize the impact of a situation.

8. Simile

The other figurative language used in album "The Car" is simile. As stated by Rendo and Hendar (2025), simile constitutes a rhetorical device, one in which a comparison is established between two objects or ideas through the utilization of words or phrases such as "like," "as," "than," "similar to," or "resemble." Simile is generally the comparison of two things essentially unlike, on the basis of a resemblance in one aspect. The example, "*It's like your little directorial debut,*" uses "like" to compare a situation to a "directorial debut," implying that it feels new, ambitious, or self-orchestrated, much like a first-time film or theater direction.

The phrase identified considered a simile because it establishes a comparison between two unlike entities using a connective word, thereby enriching the lyrics with vivid imagery and

nuanced meaning. This aligns with Rendo and Hendar's (2025) definition of a simile as a rhetorical device that compares two essentially dissimilar objects or ideas through words such as "like," based on a shared aspect.

9. Synecdoche

The last figurative language used in album "The Car" is synecdoche. Perrine (2017) stated that synecdoche is a figure of speech that employs a part of a whole or a whole of a part to represent the other. One example, "*Mr. Schwartz is havin' tea with the grips,*" uses "the grips," referring to specific film crew members who handle equipment, to represent the entire behind-the-scenes team or crew.

The phrase identified considered as synecdoche because it uses a part to represent a whole, creating a concise and evocative reference within the lyrics. This aligns with Perrine's (2017) definition of synecdoche as a figure of speech that employs a part of a whole or a whole for a part to represent the other.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This research analysed the use of figurative language in the album *The Car* by Arctic Monkeys. The study used a descriptive qualitative research design. Data was collected through active listening and lyric analysis from the Genius website. The data collection was guided by Perrine's (2017) framework. This framework categorizes figurative language into 12 types. These types are simile, metaphor, personification, apostrophe, synecdoche, metonymy, symbol, allegory, paradox, hyperbole, understatement, and irony. The analysis found 64 examples of figurative language in the songs on the album: "There'd Better Be a Mirrorball," "I Ain't Quite Where I Think I Am," "Sculptures of Anything Goes," "Jet Skis on the Moat," "Body Paint," "The Car," "Big Ideas," "Hello You," "Mr. Schwartz," and "Perfect Sense." The results show that nine out of the twelve types of figurative language were used in the lyrics. Metaphor was the most

frequently used (22 instances), followed by symbol (14 instances), irony (11 instances), personification (7 instances), hyperbole (4 instances), paradox (3 instances), understatement (1 instance), simile (1 instance), and synecdoche (1 instance). Notably, apostrophe, metonymy, and allegory were absent from the album's lyrics. This analysis confirms that figurative language plays a crucial role in enhancing the artistic expression of album "The Car", making the lyrics more engaging. By examining the deeper meanings in the lyrics, this analysis contributes to a deeper understanding of Arctic Monkeys' creative use of language in the alternative rock genre and highlights the significance of figurative language in contemporary music.

Future studies could analyse figurative language in other Arctic Monkeys albums, such as "AM" or "Tranquility Base Hotel & Casino", to compare how the band's use of figurative language evolves across their discography. In addition, future researchers could examine figurative language in other musical genres, such as jazz, hip-hop, or folk, to identify genre-specific patterns and differences in the use of figurative expressions. These recommendations aim to build on the current final report's results and encourage further exploration of figurative language's role in music

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